

PHARMACOGNOSTIC ANALYSIS OF *CONVOLVULUS ARVENSIS* LINN AND ITS EVALUATION OF VARIOUS SOLVENT EXTRACTS FOR ANTIFUNGAL AND ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVITY

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Abstract

The traditional plants found throughout the world contain many medicinally important constituents but these need to be investigated for their phytochemistry, biological and pharmacological activities. In Pakistan many plants are found which are believed to be medicinally important. In the current study, *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn whole plant was investigated for their pharmacognostic analysis and biological activities. Quantitative pharmacognostic analysis showed that the extract contains total ash value of 10.4% and moisture content 1.04%. Organoleptic characteristics, macroscopic and anatomical studies were performed. The antifungal activity was evaluated employing five fungal pores and the result revealed that this plant has strongest antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* and lowest against *Aspergillus fumigatus*. The highest percentage inhibition of α -amylase for *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn was shown by the ethanolic extract i.e. 35.43% which shows that the plant is antidiabetic. The current study suggests that the plant has different phytochemical and biological activities but selection of solvent system is the key to explore comprehensive biological actions of plants and isolation of commercially potential compounds.

1. INTRODUCTION

Plants make many chemical compounds which have different biological functions. These may include defense against fungi, insects, and bacteria and viruses. Approximately

12000 such compounds have been identified so far. The compounds isolated from medicinal plants have different actions against one's body through mechanisms similar to those already well recognized for the chemical compounds in traditional medicines thus herbal drugs do not vary much from traditional medicines with regard to their mechanism and mode of action. The herbal drugs have useful pharmacological actions but they have some adverse drugs reactions as well like conventional drugs. The plant material has different compounds which have different undesired effects though these effects may be minimized by different methods and processes (Ali *et al.*, 2001). [1]

Convolvulus arvensis Linn belongs to the family of Convolvulaceae. *Convolvulus* is a genus of about 250 species of flowering plants distributed throughout the world. In Pakistan, it is found in topical and hilly regions. The plant contains glycosides, lipids, alkaloids, phenols and many more phytochemicals. (Manbir *et al.*, 2012) [2]. The alkaloid called polyhydroxytropine from the roots of this plant exhibited significant inhibitory activity towards α -galactosidase and β -glucosidase. The rhizome and a paste made from it is a diuretic, cholagogue, cathartic and significant aperient. The alcoholic and aqueous extract showed moderate tranquilizing antihemorrhagic activity. Also these extracts showed antifungal and antibacterial effects. These extracts were found to cause no harm for kidney and liver functions. These extracts were also found to minimize uterine and intestinal pain (Manbir *et al.*, 2012). [2]

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethanol, methanol, acetone, chloroform, distilled water, DMSO, Clotrimazole, phosphate buffer, sodium chloride, sodium phosphate buffer.

2.1: Collection and identification:

The *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn was collected from District Peshawar, Pakistan and was kindly identified by Dr. Haroon Khan, Faculty of Pharmacy, Gomal University, Pakistan.

2.2: Preparation of extract:

The whole plant was shade dried for 4 weeks at the room temperature. The dried material was comminuted by mortar and pestle and electric grinder to coarse powder with a final dry weight of 1 kg. The extracts were prepared by macerating 200 mg of powder separately in five different solvents with varying polarity from highly non polar to highly polar solvents including chloroform, acetone, ethyl alcohol, methanol and distilled water. Powder was placed in separate Erlenmeyer flask for 3 days and occasionally mixed with by ultrasonic bath five times a day. The ultrasonic bath was operated at 40 KHz and 25 °C. Afterward the extract was filtered through filtration and the residue was again dipped into the respective solvents. This process was performed three times. After that all the respective filtrates were collected and concentrated by rotary evaporator to acquire the crude extract of each solvent.

2.3: Pharmacognostic analysis:

2.3.1: Quantitative pharmacognostic analysis:

2.3.1 a: Determination of moisture content:

2 gram of powder was taken in crucible and was kept in oven for 24 hr. at 105°C. This initial weight was assigned as W1. Then it was weighed after 24 hr. and again kept in oven for next 24 hr. Then it was again weighed after 24 hr. and this weight was assigned as W2 and the % moisture content was determined by the formula

$$\% \text{ moisture content} = (W1 - W2 / W1) \times 100$$

2.3.1b: Determination of ash value:

3 gram of powder was taken in pre weighed crucible. Weight of crucible and powder was assigned as W1. It was heated on burner till the plant material got charred. Then it was transferred to muffle furnace and heated at 450 °C for 6 hr. A white ash was obtained which was cooled and weight using balance and this was assigned as W2. The procedure was performed both for *Rhazya stricta* Decne and *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn and ash value was determined using formula.

$$\text{Ash value} = (W1 - W2 / W1) \times 100$$

The result obtained was expressed in percentage.

2.3.2: Organoleptic and anatomical characters of plant species and extracts:

In organoleptic characters, different sensory variables of the plant powder and extracts e.g colour, odour and taste of plant were documented. These contains conclusions obtain from studies resulted due to feelings on sense organs. The anatomy of stem and root of *Convolvulus arvensis* was determined by following (Puruish *et al.*, 1996) [3] while its leaf anatomy was determined by following (Cotton *et al.*, 1974) [4] and (Clark *et al.*, 1960) [5].

2.3: Antifungal assay:

The susceptibility testing of each solvent extract of drug were performed by employing the disc diffusion method (Bibi *et al.*, 2011) [6]. The pores of selected fungal strains were harvested in 0.02% of tween 20 solution and the turbidity was balanced as stated by the McFarland turbidity standard. The prepared inocula were incubated at 37°C for 18 hrs. 100 µl of the fungal inocula were swabbed onto the petri dishes containing sabouraud dextrose agar which is the medium for fungal strains. Then the test samples (5 µl of 20 g/ml DMSO) infused filter paper discs were placed over the swabbed surface. Similarly, discs impregnated with 5 µl of reference standards (4 mg/ml DMSO) served as positive control Clotrimazole was employed as standard antifungal. For confirmation of nontoxic effect of DMSO, the DMSO impregnated discs were used as negative control. The plates were incubated for 24 hours at 28°C. Then the zone of diameter of inhibition nearby the drugs and standard treated discs were measured to nearest mm using calipers and were recorded.

2.4: In vitro antidiabetic activity determination:

The in vitro antidiabetic activity of the extracts was found by employing the standard protocol with slight modifications (Arunachalam *et al.*, 2013) [7] For determination of inhibition assay of α -amylase activity, 500 μ l of the sample was taken and 500 μ l of 0.02M of phosphate buffer containing 0.5mg/ml α -amylase was introduced into it and the mixture was incubated for 15 minutes at 25°C. The pH of phosphate buffer was 6.9 with 0.006M sodium chloride. After pre incubation, 500 μ l of 1% starch solution in 0.02M sodium phosphate buffer was introduced to each test tube at an interval of 5 seconds. This reaction mixture was then incubated at 25°C for 10 minutes. After the said time interval, 1ml of DNSA colour was added to cease the reaction. These test tubes were then incubated for about 5 minutes in a boiling water bath and then cooled to room temperature. 10 ml of distilled water was added into the reaction mixture to dilute and then the absorbance was measured at 540 nm.

$$\%inhibition = (Abs - Abc) / Abs \times 100$$

Where Abs is the absorbance of control and Abc is the absorbance of sample.

2.9: Data analysis:

Each assay was performed three times in this experiment. The data was presented as \pm standard deviation. Mean values of different were subjected to analysis of variance.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1: Pharmacognostic analysis:

3.1 a: Quantitative pharmacognostic analysis:

The detailed study of organoleptic properties of ash values and fluorescent behavior of *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn whole plant can easily identified and differentiated from their possible adulterants by these parameters. Ash values of the drug represent an idea about the presence of inorganic matter and other compounds besides the actual drug. The total ash value was found to be 10.40 and moisture content was 1.04%

3.1b: Organoleptic characters of plant species:

The organoleptic characters of *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn whole plant are outlined in table 1.

3.1c: Organoleptic characters of extracts:

The extracts of *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn were observed for their physical look and other organoleptic properties. These organoleptic properties are outlined in table 2.

3.2: Antifungal activity determination:

Disc diffusion method was performed to find the antifungal activity of *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn. Different extracts *Convolvulus arvensis* showed good antifungal activities against various strains. The highest antifungal activity by the plant were shown by the

methanolic and ethanolic extracts while chloroform showed some activity as well. The least activity was shown by the distilled water extract. The standard drug Clotrimazole showed maximum activity with 31 mm. From literature review it is known that all parts of *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn are used to treat antifungal diseases which support this study. The antifungal activity of the plant is shown in table 3.

Table 1: Macroscopic and anatomical studies of *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn

Part	Property	Fresh	Dry
Root	Colour	White	White
	Odour	Indistinct	Indistinct
	Shape	Cylindrical	Cylindrical
	Texture	Hairy	Hairy
	Rootless	Present	Present
	Direction of growth	Vertical	Vertical
Stem	Colour	Green	Green
	Odour	Indistinct	Indistinct
	Shape	Angular	Angular
	Kind	Herbaceous	Herbaceous
	Direction of growth	Prostate	Prostate
Leaf	Colour	Dark green	Light green
	Dimension	Length is 4.2 cm, width is 1.1 cm	Length is 4 cm, width is 1 cm
	Composition	Simple	Simple
	Shape	Hastate	Hastate
	Apex	Obtuse	Obtuse

Table 2: Organoleptic characters of extracts

Extract	Part	Solvent	Colour	Odour	Nature	Taste
<i>C. arvensis</i> Linn	Whole	Methanol	Metallic oak	Indistinct	Sticky	Sweet

Table 3: In vitro antifungal activity of extract *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn and its fractions

Extracts (20 mg/ml)	Diameter of zone of inhibition in mm				
	<i>A. fumigatus</i>	<i>F. solani</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>
Chloroform	8	10	13	12	10
Acetone	-	-	9	7	-
Ethanol	8	11	14	15	12
Methanol	9	11	14	17	12
Distilled water	-	-	-	9	-
Negative Control	-	-	-	-	-

- -: Not active
- Negative control: DMSO

3.4: Antidiabaetic activity determination:

The results of antidiabaetic activity showed by the plants is summarized in the table 4. The results obtained suggests that *C. arvensis* Linn is effective to lowers the blood glucose level i.e the plant contains antidiabaetic potential. The ethanolic extract of the

plant showed maximum inhibition of the enzyme as compared to other fractions. On the other hand, the water fraction showed less inhibition of the enzyme for *C. Arvensis* Linn.

Table 4: % inhibition of α -amylase

Extract	% inhibition <i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> Linn
Chloroform	31.88
Acetone	28.50
Ethanol	35.43
Methanol	33.67
Distilled water	24.15

4. CONCLUSION

The results showed in this study that *Convolvulus arvensis* Linn whole plant may be used to treat infections caused by various fungal strains but possible route of administration is yet to be found. Furthermore, the plant is antidiabetic but more work is needed to find the route of administration. The selection of solvent system to make its extract is also important. The plant is suspected to treat many diseases as it contains many phytochemicals but further research is needed to find its pharmacological activities.

References

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